

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The teacher of higher education should motivate students to use modern information technology training to study the discipline and develop professional competencies in foreign language teaching. The purpose of this research is to highlight the problem of finding the optimal didactic capabilities of modern information technologies used for improving the system of training specialists in the field of foreign languages teaching and to discuss the results of current studies in this direction.

Keywords: modern technologies; foreign language teaching; multimedia technology; online platform; testing program.

Introduction. Because of scientific and technological progress, the use of new technologies in various spheres of human activity imposes new requirements for the training of future specialists in the condition of formalization of education. At the present stage of development of education. In this regard, the purpose of the study is to teach future teachers the ability to competently work with various kinds of information, to make the most of the opportunities of modern information technologies for professional improvement in the field of teaching foreign languages. Implementation of the technological approach in the preparation of the future teacher of English is hampered by the following contradictions:

Reserch methodology. In the process of research the following methods were used: theoretical (analysis of pedagogical, psychological, methodical literature, normative and program – methodical documentation, Internet resources; generalization; forecasting, design and modelling), diagnostic (questioning, testing), empirical (pedagogical observation), experimental (pedagogical experiment) and methods of graphic representation of results.

Analysis and Results. One of the most promising technologies for teaching a foreign language and monitoring the quality of education in recent years is the language portfolio. In modern domestic pedagogy, some scientists, for example, V.B. Uspensky, A.P. Chernyavskaya consider Portfolio as a method of training designed to systematize accumulated experience, knowledge, and more clearly determine the direction of their development [3]. A number of Russian scientists consider the "Portfolio of the student" to be completely new technologies, only making their way to life. This is the opinion of E.S. Polat, M.Yu. Bukharkina, M.V. Moiseeva, A.E. Petrova and others who consider the "Portfolio of the pupil" primarily a means of learning self-esteem [3]. We believe that the "Student Portfolio" can act as a 5 Образовательный процесс Выпуск №3, 2018 component of the technology of organizing independent learning activity and professional-personal self-development of students in foreign language classes, representing a method of teaching and the form of organizing independent student learning activities, undoubtedly being a means of forming the necessary skills of reflection of one's own activity; introspection, reflection, an instrument of self-evaluation of his own cognitive, creative work. In our opinion, as a means of introducing and expanding personal-oriented and individualized education in higher education, it seems possible to develop the formation of the Portfolio - the educational "Portfolio" of the student (or the package of educational educational products of the student: Learning Educational Activities Packet = LEAP)[2].

"Student Portfolio" is a set of documents, independent works of the student, which reflects his efforts, progress and achievements in one or several areas. When studying a foreign language at a university, it is advisable to start the formation of the "Portfolio" of educational products from the beginning of the first semester and continue until the exam. An approximate list of methodological products of the students, included in the "Portfolio" and developed by the author:

1. Results of diagnostic tests and their analysis.
2. Results of control works and their analysis.
3. Abstracts (individual reading).
4. Description of the preparation and participation in a scientific student conference.

5. Participation in the essay competition.
6. Materials of individual project activity.
7. Self-reflection of educational activity for semesters.
8. Self-evaluation of work.

It was noted that students are very interested in the practice of drawing up their training "Portfolios", they work with enthusiasm. They create an integral picture of objective progress in a certain area. In the process of organizing pedagogical support for students in the study of the subject "Foreign Language", project activities can also be carried out in the form of a "case" method [4].

Case studies (case studies) have traditionally been used in training, where the trainee is offered specific situations from practice. The basis of information technology of foreign language learning is computer training, the successful implementation of which (in addition to the computer as the main technical means) requires special didactic tools and thoughtful methods of working with them. In the second stage, students developed multimedia products for teaching and learning English. The use of new tools has significantly transformed the traditional scheme of organization of the process of training, ensuring the development and implementation in practice of the variable structure of the educational process of higher education with components that allow automating many processes [4].

The usage of Internet has brought tremendous change in the field of teaching and enhancing English learning. It is believed that people tend to forget everything within three days after they hear. How to Use these Technologies:

1. Video Tapes Scenes from popular English films can be screened first without any running script on the scene. Then the students are asked to identify the words, script etc. Again the scene will be repeated with the scripts on the scene.
2. Communication Labs Software's are available to develop LSRW skills. By incorporating suitable software through computers the students will play it again and again with their own interest and try to improve their LSRW skills, which are most essential in this modernized IT world.
3. Video Library. This is helpful for the students to those who miss some interesting session. In this process the teaching of the faculty will be recorded and made available to the students. The students can view the tapes in their leisure hours. The advantage in this method is that students can replay it when there is a necessity.
4. Internet. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the

students to find out the suitable materials for them. Students are instructed to do the grammar exercises which are available online. Through Internet we can collect data from various sources for any instruction [7]

The use of various technologies allows implementing a differentiated approach to students by creating conditions for their independent work. A methodically well-constructed online material helps to replace the means of paper visibility, frees the teacher from writing on the board and allows one to trace the material of the lesson in dynamics. The great advantage of using technologies in comparison with traditional means of visualization is the convenience of their storage and distribution with the ability to copy and edit.

Colourful on-screen training material increases the interest and motivation of students to learn. According to the method of using technology in teaching foreign languages, we implement three models of classes:

1. In demo mode (one computer on the teacher's desk + projector);
2. In the individual mode (occupation in a computer class without access to the Internet);
3. In individual remote mode (class in the computer room with Internet access).

To obtain relevant information, it is necessary to develop students' skills of searching for it in a constantly updated resource – the Internet [2]. To do this, students are offered our catalogues of public sites and various online tools. In the third stage, the experimental work was carried out to identify the impact of multimedia technologies on the academic performance of students. The study was conducted in two groups, one experimental and the other control; each group had 25 students. Both groups were equivalent in the direction of training, academic performance and teaching program. In the first group (experimental) multimedia technologies were used in the educational process, and in the second group (control) the educational process was organized by the traditional method.

Discussions: We consider highly effective the use of the educational "Portfolio" in the process of studying at the university, a step-by-step documented fixation of the student's achievements takes place in using modern technology and the student feels himself a real participant in the educational process, whose interests are not indifferent to the teacher and the group members.

Conclusion recommendations. In recent years, new technologies have had a significant impact on the improvement of the education system and have been an important focus of the restructuring of both general and higher education. The main educational value of information technologies is that they allow creating a multisensory interactive learning environment with almost unlimited potential opportunities, which

appear in the teaching and learning environment. In contrast to the technical means of education, information technology allows not only to saturate teaching with a large amount of knowledge, but also to develop the intellectual and creative abilities of students, their ability to acquire new knowledge as well as to work with various sources of information. Using the above information, educational technology for teaching foreign languages helps to increase motivation to study a particular discipline, deeper assimilation of the material, the development of skills of search, analysis and structuring of information and, ultimately, the formation of general cultural and professional competencies defined in modern state educational institutions of higher education.

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